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Stepwise Stability Constants of Mn(II) and Co(II) Complexes with 2-Hydroxy-5-Chlorobenzophenoneanil

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Manuscript received 9 November 1977; revised 19 September 1978, accepted 22 February 1979

THE proton ligand stability constant and the stepwise formation constants of the complexes have been determined by the Calvin Bjerrum pH titration technique as used by Irving and Rossotti¹.

The complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) with (HCBA) have been studied potentiometrically^{2,3}. The present investigation deals with the potentiometric studies of complexes of Mn(II) and Co(II) with 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenone and (HCBA).

Experimental

The same experimental procedure as described in our another communication² was followed.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (0.5 M) keeping the total volume of 40 ml.

(I) 0.8 ml. (0.998 M) $HClO_4$ + 4.0 ml. (1 M) $NaClO_4$ + 11.2 ml. water + 24.0 ml. dioxane. (II) 0.8 ml. (0.998 M) $HClO_4$ + 4.0 ml. (1 M) $NaClO_4$ + 11.2 ml. water + 2.0 ml. (0.01 M) ligand + 22.0 ml. dioxane. (III) 0.8 ml. (0.998 M) $HClO_4$ + 4.0 ml. (1.0 M) $NaClO_4$ + 10.8 ml. water + 2.0 ml. (0.1 M) ligand + 0.4 ml. (0.1 M) metal + 22.0 ml. dioxane.

The average number of protons associated with HCBA ($\bar{n}_4$), average number of ligand attached per metal ion ($\bar{n}$) and free ligand exponent (pL) were calculated using the formulae of Irving and Rossotti¹.

Fig. 1 Formation curves of (A) $Mn(HCBA)_2$ and (B) $Co(HCBA)_2$ at 30°C.

From the values of $\bar{n}$ and pL formation curves were plotted (Fig. 1) and the formation constants were determined by the usual computational methods. The values of formation constants obtained from least square method are summarised below:

TABLE

Temp. $30 \pm 2^\circ$; $\mu = 0.1 M$ in 60% v/v dioxane-water media

Chelate	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta$
HCBA	10.85	3.64	14.49
$Mn(HCBA)_2$	5.68	3.89	9.57
$Co(HCBA)_2$	6.48	4.27	10.75

Results and Discussion

In the ligand it is the chelated phenolic-OH group which takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during the formation of metal chelate. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, the number of dissociable protons attached per ligand molecule is equal to one.

In the initial stage of the titration the ligand curve got shifted to the left (or above) as compared to the free acid curve due to the basic property of the tertiary nitrogen ($-C=N$) which accepts a proton from the strongly acid medium. The protonated species formed

dissociates in two steps as below :

The formation curve of the ligand extends over a range ($0.4 < \bar{n}_d < 1.9$) and indicates the formation of the species HL and H_2L^+ i.e., phenolic hydrogen and protonated nitrogen are completely dissociable. $\log p_{K_1}\text{H}$ and $\log p_{K_2}\text{H}$ belongs to the formation of HL and H_2L^+ species respectively.

The depression of the metal – titration curves below the ligand titration curve at the pH values much below the pH of metal ion hydrolysis confirms the complexation between the ligand and metal ions. The proton of the phenolic OH group has been replaced by the metal and the chelation takes place through phenolate oxygen and azomethine nitrogen.

There was no precipitation upto $\text{pH} = 9.25$ for Mn^{2+} and 9.50 for Co^{2+} . The values of $\bar{n}$ obtained were more than 1.0 at higher pH values suggesting 1 : 2 complexation.

The order of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ of Mn^{2+} and Co^{2+} was $\text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+}$ which was according to the Irving – Williams rule⁵.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. K.A. Thaker, Head of the Chemistry Department, for providing necessary research facilities. We are also thankful to Saurashtra University for providing the scholarship to one of them (Y.Z.P.)

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Studies on Dioctyltin Dithiocarbamates

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Manuscript received to October 1978 ; accepted 12 March 1979

IN continuation of our studies on diorganotin dithiocarbamates¹, the present communication reports the synthesis and characterisation of a series of new dioctyltin derivatives. Analytical, conductance, molecular weight, thermogravimetric data, IR, PMR and electronic spectral studies have been made to establish the structure of the newly synthesized compounds.

Experimental

Dioctyltin oxide was obtained from Alfa Inorganics (U. S. A.). Amines and solvents were purified by conventional methods². Physico-chemical measurements were made as reported earlier¹.

The newly synthesized dioctyltin bis (dithiocarbamates) were prepared by insertion of carbon disulphide to amine and dioctyltin oxide mixture, as represented below

A representative experiment for the preparation of dioctyltin bis (dithiocarbamates) is described below.

To a mixture of dioctyltin oxide (10 mmole) and carbon disulphide (10 ml) in chloroform (20 ml) a solution of morpholine (20 mmole) in chloroform (10 ml) was added dropwise at -20° . After stirring for about two hrs., excess chloroform was distilled off under reduced pressure. The resulting brown viscous liquid was extracted with diethyl ether, and the product dried under vacuum (yield 70%).

Results and Discussion

The compounds are yellow to brown, high boiling oily liquids except piperidine and diphenyl derivatives which are sharp melting solids. They are soluble in chloroform, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, methanol and dichloromethane. The molecular weight determination in (freezing) benzene (cryoscopic method) and electrical conductance measurements in methanol indicate their monomeric and non-electrolytic behaviour.

Thermogravimetric analysis of dioctyltin bis (piperidine dithiocarbamate) was carried out at a heating rate of $5^\circ/\text{minute}$. Results indicate that it slowly decomposes at -100° liberating carbon disulphide. The residual weight at 260° corresponds to an equimolar mixture of dioctyltin sulphide and bis (piperidine) thiourea,